

ANALYSIS OF FAMILY RELATIONS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LITERATURE BASED ON THE WORKS OF JANE AUSTEN “PRIDE AND PREJUDICE” AND THE ASKAD OF MUKHTOR “CHINAR”

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Abstract: The article analyzes family relations in English and Uzbek literature based on the novels “Pride and Prejudice” by Jane Austen and “Chinor” Askad Mukhtor. Both works reflect the cultural and social norms of their time, focusing on the role of the family in shaping the personality of the characters. It examines how social expectations and traditional values affect the relationship between characters, especially in the context of the position of women in the family. The conflict between traditional family responsibilities and personal aspirations of the characters is explored, emphasizing the importance of the family as an institution and personal space.

Keywords: family relations, traditional values, English literature, Uzbek literature, Jane Austen, Askad Mukhtor, the role of a woman, social expectations, marriage, personal aspirations.

Аннотация: В тезисе анализируются семейные отношения в английской и узбекской литературе на основе романов “Гордость и Предубеждение” Джейн Остин и “Чинор” Аскада Мухтора. Оба произведения отражают культурные и социальные нормы своего времени, акцентируя внимание на роли семьи в формировании личности героев. Рассматривается, как социальные ожидания и традиционные ценности влияют на взаимоотношения между персонажами, особенно в контексте положения женщин в семье. Исследуется конфликт между традиционными семейными обязанностями и личными устремлениями героев, подчеркивая важность семьи как института и личного пространства.

Ключевые слова: семейные отношения, традиционные ценности, английская литература, узбекская литература, Джейн Остин, Аскад Мухтор, роль женщины, социальные ожидания, брак, личные стремления.

In the novels “Pride and Prejudice” by Jane Austen and “Chinor” Askad Mukhtor, family relationships are presented as a reflection of the cultural and social norms of their time. Both works emphasize the importance of the family in

shaping the personality of the characters, but also focus on the conflict between traditional values and individual aspirations, especially in relation to women. Relationships within the family serve both as a mechanism of social pressure and as a space for personal searches of heroes.

The novels focus on the meaning of marriage, social norms, and personal values. Both works show how social expectations and economic status influence the choice of a partner, however, while in the English novel the emphasis is on individual freedom and love, in Uzbek literature family traditions and respect for elders occupy a central place.

Family relationships in the novels *Pride and Prejudice* by Jane Austen and *Chinor* Askad Mukhtor represent a complex dynamic reflecting the cultural, social and historical contexts of 19th century England and 20th century Uzbekistan. Both works emphasize the importance of the family as a key institution of society, influencing the formation of personality, social status and personal destinies of the characters.

In *Pride and Prejudice*, Jane Austen explores family relationships through the prism of British social norms, where marriage and family unions are seen as a means of ensuring financial stability and strengthening social status. Special attention is paid to the role of women in family relationships, where heroines such as Elizabeth Bennet face social pressure and family expectations, but at the same time strive for independence and self-expression. Elizabeth Bennet rejects traditional views on marriage as an economic union and defends the right to a love marriage, which puts her in opposition to patriarchal foundations.

Askad Mukhtor's novel *Chinor* examines family relations in the context of Uzbek culture and traditions, where the institution of the family plays an important role as a guardian of cultural heritage and traditional values. In Uzbek literature, the family is often depicted as a collective unit, where individual interests are subordinated to common goals and maintaining the reputation of the family. However, as in Austen's novel, *Chinor*'s characters face conflicts between traditional values and personal aspirations. Relationships between family members are built on the basis of deep cultural roots, where respect for elders, preservation of traditions and duty to the family play a primary role.

Social expectations and pressures. In both works, the authors emphasize that family relationships are inextricably linked to social norms and expectations. In Jane Austen's novel *Pride and Prejudice*, marriage is seen as a means of ensuring financial stability and status, whereas in Askad Mukhtor's novel *Chinor*, family ties play an important role in preserving traditional values.

The role of women in the family. Both English and Uzbek literature raise the topic of the position of women in family relations. Lizzie Bennett from *Pride and Prejudice* strives to marry for love, rather than submit to social pressure. In "Chinor", the heroines face the expectations of a traditional society, where a woman is often perceived as the guardian of the home and family.

Family values and their conflict with personal desires. In both novels, the characters face a conflict between family responsibilities and personal aspirations. In *Pride and Prejudice*, family expectations often contradict the characters' desire for personal happiness. *Chinor* also touches on the theme of the internal conflict between traditional family values and modern views.

Both novels show that family relationships are shaped by social and cultural expectations, but at the same time, internal aspirations for freedom, self-expression and happiness turn out to be important factors in the development of the characters' character. In *Pride and Prejudice*, the characters strive to find a balance between social expectations and personal feelings, while in *Chinor*, the characters face the need to reconcile their aspirations with traditions and responsibilities to the family. Thus, both works raise questions about the role of the family in human life, its impact on personal choices and social status, as well as the possibility of changing traditional foundations in the face of changing times.

In both novels, the family serves as both a means of social control and an arena for personal searches, where the characters fight for their rights to happiness, self-realization and the preservation of their own values, while remaining part of a complex network of family and cultural obligations.

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